

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA, ACTIVITY LEVELS, METHODS OF TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF DERMATOMYOSITIS AND SYSTEMIC VASCULITIS. PHARMACODYNAMICS OF DRUGS USED IN THE TREATMENT OF DERMATOMYOSITIS AND SYSTEMIC VASCULITIS

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Annotation: This article discusses in detail the diagnostic criteria, activity levels, methods of treatment of dermatomyositis and systemic vasculitis, the pharmacodynamics of drugs used in the treatment of dermatomyositis, its main features and additional treatment methods.

Key words: dermatomyositis, pharmacodynamics, polymyositis, inflammation, pathomorphological transformation.

Dermatomyositis is a disease in which motor functions are affected by intense redness of the skin as a result of dilation of capillaries. However, if it does not affect the skin, the disease is called polymyositis (a systemic inflammation of the muscles that affects the linear muscles of the legs and arms). The disease can occur at a young age, but it is called juvenile dermatomyositis. In combination with polymyositis, systemic rheumatic diseases characterized by inflammation and pain of the muscles are formed in the muscle tissue.

There are different signs of the inflammatory nature of the skin, which appear at different stages separately or in combination. In dermatomyositis, skin changes appear early in muscle tissue - over months and even years. There are the following main symptoms of the disease:

- rash in the form of papules, blisters;
- swelling of the skin and subcutaneous bleeding;
- redness on the eyelids, near the eyes, on the lips, cheeks, back, neck, side walls of the nose;
- red, pink, peeling spots on the joints of the fingers, knees;
- excessive dryness of the skin;
- brittleness of nails.

Often the doctor prescribes other non-drug methods used in the treatment of dermatomyositis. It is important to follow the expert's recommendations. Depending on the severity of the symptoms, doctors prescribe additional treatments:

- treatment of dermatomyositis with exercise to improve muscle function and maintain the elasticity of muscle tissue;
- speech therapy. The patient has weakness of the swallowing muscles due to dermatomyositis.

Dermatomyositis is difficult to treat, but with patience you can achieve results using folk remedies.

It should be borne in mind that herbal treatment is used during periods of reduced symptoms and clear symptoms. Treatment is carried out in spring and autumn to prevent exacerbation of the disease. The course of treatment lasts one month.

The defining symptom in the clinic of dermatomyositis is the defeat of the linear muscles. Weakness in the muscles of the neck, characterized by lower and proximal parts, upper limbs make it difficult to perform daily tasks. In severe lesions, patients can barely get out of bed, cannot hold their head, move independently, and hold objects in their hands.

The main diagnostic signs of dermatomyositis are characteristic clinical manifestations of skin and muscle injuries; pathomorphological transformation of muscle fibers; increase in serum enzyme levels; typical electromyographic changes. Additional criteria for the diagnosis of dermatomyositis include dysphagia and calcinosis.

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